

Indocyanine green as a promising tool for parathyroid identification during surgery

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Abstract:

Insufficient blood perfusion and insufficient venous drainage have been highlighted as potential risk factors for postoperative parathyroid malfunction. Intraoperative assessment of parathyroid gland perfusion is usually estimated by the surgeon according to the color of the gland and visible bleeding at the edge. Indocyanine green with the use of intra-operative IR scopes are used as a tool for parathyroid blood supply identification and preservation. It is useful to identify and localize Parathyroid gland and to assess parathyroid blood perfusion. Thus, the ischemic parathyroid gland can be removed and re-transplanted to avoid post operative hypoparathyroidism. It can decrease the post-operative hypoparathyroidism but does not replace surgical expertise. Redo surgeries with extensive fibrosis and neo vessel formation had hampered visualization.

Neurotological Management Of Hemifacial Spasm

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Abstract:

Objective: Hemi facial spasm is a disease of the facial nerve that is successfully treated by microsurgical decompression at the root of the facial nerve at the cerebello pontine angle. By using the RETROLABYRINTHINE APPROACH to the cerebello pontine angle, the morbidity and mortality of the surgery has decreased, since there is no need to retract the cerebellum.

Method: Two cases with hemi facial spasm are presented, along with a brief literature review concerning the diagnosis and microsurgical decompression of the root of the facial nerve, at the cerebellum pontine angle, using a RETROLABYRINTHINE approach.

Results: I studied a patient with 13 years history of hemi facial spasm, clinically and with M.R.I. with contrast of the brain. A diagnosis of micro vascular compression of the root of the facial nerve was done. The patient was operated by the retro labyrinthine approach, performing a microvascular decompression of the root of the facial nerve with a complete resolution of her hemi facial spasm.

I present a second patient with a history of 17 years with the disease, treated by the same approach.

Conclusion: The microvascular decompression of the facial nerve by the retro labyrinthine approach is a safe and successful treatment.

Beyond Sinuses: Our Experience.

Dr. Jaya Kochure

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Abstract:

Introduction: Invention of endoscopes, its optics and use of Video monitors has proven to be a boon in Sinus surgeries. With time its application beyond sinuses into the neighbouring structures has made it possible to operate in these areas with comparative ease with less morbidity, as compared to open approach.

For past few years it's a routine now all over the world to perform advanced endoscopic surgeries, especially Skull base after acquiring adequate training.

We would like to share our experience at our centre.

Materials & Methods: A retrospective study of 40 advanced trans nasal endoscopic surgeries between a period 2007-2019.

Surgeries included are Trans Sphenoidal Pituitary tumour excision (majority) and few Endoscopic CSF Rhinorrhea repair, Endoscopic Optic Nerve decompression etc.

Summary & Conclusion: As a team of ENT Surgeon & Neurosurgeon with proper co-ordination using 4 hands techniques we could achieve a fair outcome. With time, imbibing new techniques, tips & tricks complications can be reduced

Hub and spike model to screen newborn babies for hearing disabilities at the primary health care centers.

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Abstract:

Incidence: Incidence of hearing impairment is higher in developing countries especially in rural areas because of inadequate health care facilities. In India, 4 in every 1000 children suffer from severe to profound hearing loss. The estimated prevalence of childhood onset deafness in India was found to be 2% [4]. The National sample survey 58th round (2002) surveyed disability in Indian households and found that hearing disability was 2nd most common cause of disability and top most cause of sensory deficit.

Origin of the Research problem: Hearing impairment is a serious and grossly neglected condition in India because of the poor socio-economic status being the majority. At rural areas, the population cannot be screened and diagnosed with hearing disabilities due to lack of facilities available at the primary health care centres. There is a desperate need to make the appropriate facilities available for screening and diagnosing the new born babies at rural areas.

The problem with hearing handicapped is not just a loss to the person but its productivity loss to the nation. The cost of the implant is not only the issue but post Cochlear Implantation the AVT (Audio Visual Treatment) sessions are also a costly affair to the needy. By providing AVT at the door step it is assured that the patient is benefited medically and financially. Otherwise the patient may not come for follow up and Cochlear Implant may not help.

Significance of the Study: Early detection of the hearing impairment is extremely important for the further management and development of speech and language. The screened infants who are diagnosed with hearing disability will be subjected to further battery of investigations. This battery of tests need 3 to 4 months time for their actual curative treatment. The treatment methods will be as per required. Those benefitting with hearing aids will be advised accordingly and those not benefitted with hearing aids will be a candidate for cochlear implantation.

After cochlear implantation as a curative method, the implanty needs further AVT (Audio visual treatment) sessions frequently for the development of speech and language.

In this project we will also be training anganw

adi workers for screening babies with OAE, for our assistance. We have developed a software which will enable our assistants to report to us about the results and in return we will guide them about further processing. The same module will enable us to give the AVT sessions in the remote areas when the implantee is unable to come for follow up

Objectives:

- 1) Our objective for this project is to screen the new borns to detect hearing impairment at the earliest at primary health care centres.
- 2) Provide further modality of treatment for the hearing impairment patients at Dr. D. Y. Patil Hospital & Research centre.

Obstructive Sleep Apnea In Children

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Abstract:

Objective: MEDICAL MANAGEMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA IN CHILDREN.

Symptoms/Signs Of Obstructive Sleep Apnea In Children are Snoring, Restless sleep, Nocturnal sweating, Morning headache, Mouth breathing, Problems with concentration, Excessive daytime sleep, Nocturnal enuresis. Etiology risk factors for osa in children includes Enlarged Adenoids and Tonsils are the common , Certain dental abnormalities e.g. large bite, Obesity, Candid facial abnormalities e.g. micrognathia, drugs (sedative), Mucopolysaccharides, Disorders causing hypertonia, hypotonia e.g down syndrome, cerebral palsy, Possibly genetic factors.

On average 4 children are seen every week in the outpatients department at Morning Rise Private Clinic. Total of 205 children, 113 males and 92 females where seen from January to September 2019. 196 patients have successfully been managed without surgical intervention. 9 patients further went for the surgery

Examination: Reveals the following: Enlarged Adenoids, Enlarged Tonsils, Enlarged both Adenoids and Tonsils, Wet Nasal cavity, the colour of the turbinate appears purple. Complications includes Growth disturbance, Cor pulmonale, and pulmonary hypertension, and Learning or behavior disturbance, recurrent ear infection.

Treatment: Due to the non- availability of ENT specialists and ENT facilities, at Morning Rise Private Clinic, we opt to treat obstructive sleep apnea due to Adenoiditis and Tonsillitis medically taking into accounts the following thorough investigations e.g. Nasal swab for culture sensitivity result Allergy profile. Anti- allergy drugs, Antibiotic after culture sensitivity, Nasal spray when necessary. Long acting penicillin injection which is given at 3 weekly interval followed by monthly interval for 3 months. The period of treatment comes to a total of four months. 85% of the children do very well. 15% may proceed for Tonsillectomy, Adenoidectomy or Adeno -Tonsillectomy.

Conclusion: Obstructive Sleep apnea must be assessed physically to look at the tonsils, adenoids, mucosal appearance, radiological investigation, allergy profile to arrive at the diagnosis before initiating surgical intervention. This will help manage children with problems of sleep apnea who may not be able to see ENT specialists. This has reduced referral to the only major referral hospital in the country where the ENT specialists are, for people have to travel for more than 500 – 1000km to seek ENT services.

Morning Rise Private Clinic came in to mitigate the shortage of ENT specialists in the country.

Finally, we are seeking for Co-operating partners to open a state of the art ENT Specialist Hospital in Zambia on partnership.